

Luhn prime numbers

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Abstract

The first prime number with the special property that its addition with reversal gives as result a prime number too is 229. The prime numbers with this property will be called *Luhn prime numbers*. In this article we intend to present a performing algorithm for determining the *Luhn prime numbers*. Using the presented algorithm all the 50598 *Luhn prime numbers* have been, for p prime smaller than $2 \cdot 10^7$.

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1. Introduction

The number 229 is the smallest prime number that added with his reverse gives as result a prime number, too. As $1151 = 229 + 922$ is prime.

The first that noted this special property the number 229 has, was Norman Luhn (after 9 February 1999), on the *Prime Curios* website (Caldwell & Honacher Jr., 2014). The prime numbers with this property will be later called *Luhn prime numbers*.

In the *Whats Special About This Number?* list (Friedman, 2014), a list that contains all the numbers between 1 and 9999; beside the number 229 is mentioned that his most important property is that, adding with reversal the resulting number is prime too.

The *On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, (Sloane, 2014, A061783), presents a list 1000 *Luhn prime numbers*. We owe this list to Harry J. Smith, since 28 July 2009. On the same website it is mentioned that Harvey P. Dale published on 27 November 2010 a list that contains 3000 *Luhn prime numbers* and Bruno Berselli published on 5 August 2013 a list that contains 2400 *Luhn prime numbers*.

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22 **2. Smarandache’s function**

23 The function $\mu : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$, $\mu(n) = m$, where m is the smallest natural number with the property
 24 that n divides $m!$ (or $m!$ is a multiple of n) is know in the specialty literature as Smarandache’s
 25 function, (Smarandache, 1980, 1999; Sondow & Weisstein, 2014). The values resulting from
 26 $n = 1, 2, \dots, 18$ are: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 3, 7, 4, 6, 5, 11, 4, 13, 7, 5, 6, 17, 6. These values were obtained
 27 with an algorithm that results from μ ’s definition. The program using this algorithm cannot be used
 28 for $n \geq 19$ because the numbers $19!, 20!, \dots$ are numbers which exceed the 17 decimal digits limit
 29 and the classic computing model (without the arbitrary precisions arithmetic (Uznanski, 2014))
 30 will generate errors due to the way numbers are represented in the computers memory.

31 **3. Kempner’s algorithm**

32 Kempner created an algorithm to calculate $\mu(n)$ using classical factorization $n = p_1^{p_1} \cdot p_2^{p_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_s^{p_s}$,
 33 prime number and the generalized numeration base $(\alpha_i)_{[p_i]}$, for $i = \overline{1, s}$, (Kempner, 1918). Partial
 34 solutions to the algorithm for $\mu(n)$ ’s calculation have been given earlier by Lucas and Neuberg,
 35 (Sondow & Weisstein, 2014).

36 *Remark.* If $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, n can be decomposed in a product of prime numbers $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \cdot p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_s^{\alpha_s}$,
 37 were p_i are prime numbers so that $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_s$, and $s \geq 1$, thus Kempner’s algorithm for
 38 calculating the μ function is.

$$\mu(n) = \max \left\{ p_1 \cdot (\alpha_{1[p_1]})_{(p_1)}, p_2 \cdot (\alpha_{2[p_2]})_{(p_2)}, \dots, p_s \cdot (\alpha_{s[p_s]})_{(p_s)} \right\},$$

39 where by $(\alpha_{[p]})_{(p)}$ we understand that α is ”written” in the numeration base p (noted $\alpha_{[p]}$) and it is
 40 ”read” in the p numeration base (noted $\beta_{(p)}$, were $\beta = \alpha_{[p]}$), (Smarandache, 1999, p. 39).

41 **4. Programs**

42 The list of prime numbers was generated by a program that uses the Sieve of Eratosthenes
 43 the linear version of Pritchard, Pritchard (1987), which is the fastest algorithm to generate prime
 44 numbers until the limit of L , if $L \leq 10^8$. The list of prime numbers until to $2 \cdot 10^7$ is generated in
 45 about 5 seconds. For the limit $L > 10^8$ the fastest algorithm for generating the prime numbers is
 46 the Sieve of Atkin, Atkin & Bernstein (2004).

47 **Program 4.1.** *The Program for the Sieve of Eratosthenes, the linear version of Pritchard using*
 48 *minimal memory space is:*

```
CEPbm(L) := |  $\lambda \leftarrow \text{floor} \left( \frac{L}{2} \right)$ 
              | for  $k \in 1.. \lambda$ 
              |    $is\_prime_k \leftarrow 1$ 
              |  $prime \leftarrow (2\ 3\ 5\ 7)^T$ 
              |  $i \leftarrow \text{last}(prime) + 1$ 
              | for  $j \in 4, 7.. \lambda$ 
              |    $is\_prime_j \leftarrow 0$ 
```

```

k ← 3
s ← (primek-1)2
t ← (primek)2
while t ≤ L
  for j ∈ t, t + 2 · primek..L
    is_prime $\frac{j-1}{2}$  ← 0
  for j ∈ s + 2, s + 4..t - 2
    if is_prime $\frac{j-1}{2}$  = 1
      primei ← j
      i ← i + 1
  s ← t
  k ← k + 1
  t ← (primek)2
for j ∈ s + 2, s + 4..L
  if is_prime $\frac{j-1}{2}$  = 1
    primei ← j
    i ← i + 1
return prime

```

49 **Program 4.2.** The factorization program of a natural number; this program uses the vector p
50 representing prime numbers, generated with the Sieve of Eratosthenes. The Sieve of Eratosthenes
51 is called upon through the following sequence:

$$L := 2 \cdot 10^7 \quad t_0 = \text{time}(0) \quad p := \text{CEPbm}(L) \quad t_1 = \text{time}(1)$$

$$(t_1 - t_0)s = 5.064s \quad \text{last}(p) = 1270607 \quad p_{\text{last}(p)} = 19999999$$

```

Fa(m) := return ("m = " m " > ca ultimul p2") if m > (plast(p))2
  j ← 1
  k ← 0
  f ← (1 1)
  while m ≥ pj
    if mod(m, pj) = 0
      k ← k + 1
      m ←  $\frac{m}{p_j}$ 
    otherwise
      f ← stack[f, (pj, k)] if k > 0
      j ← j + 1
      k ← 0
  f ← stack[f, (pj, k)] if k > 0
  return submatrix(f, 2, rows(f), 1, 2)

```

52

We presented the Kempner's algorithm using Mathcad programs required for the algorithm.

53 **Program 4.3.** The function counting all the digits in the p base of numeration in which is n .

$$ncb(n, p) := \begin{cases} \text{return } \text{ceil}(\log(n, p)) \text{ if } n > 1 \\ \text{return } 1 \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

54 Where $\text{ceil}(x)$ is a Mathcad function which gives the smallest integer $\geq x$ and $\log(n, p)$ is
55 logarithm in base p from n .

56 **Program 4.4.** The program intended to generate the p generalized base of numeration (noted by
57 Smarandache $[p]$) for a number with m digits.

$$a(p, m) := \begin{cases} \text{for } i \in 1..m \\ \quad a_i \leftarrow \frac{p^i - 1}{p - 1} \\ \text{return } a \end{cases}$$

58 **Program 4.5.** The program intended to generate for the p base of numeration (noted by Smaran-
59 dache (p)) to write the α number.

$$b(\alpha, p) := \begin{cases} \text{return } (1) \text{ if } p = 1 \\ \text{for } i \in 1..ncb(\alpha, p) \\ \quad b_i \leftarrow p^{i-1} \\ \text{return } b \end{cases}$$

60 **Program 4.6.** Program that determines the digits of the generalized base of numeration $[p]$ for
61 the number n .

$$Nbg(n, p) := \begin{cases} m \leftarrow ncb(n, p) \\ a \leftarrow a(p, m) \\ \text{return } (1) \text{ if } m=0 \\ \text{for } i \in m..1 \\ \quad \begin{cases} c_i \leftarrow \text{trunc}\left(\frac{n}{a_i}\right) \\ n \leftarrow \text{mod}(n, a_i) \end{cases} \\ \text{return } c \end{cases}$$

62 Where $\text{trunc}(x)$ returns the integer part of x by removing the fractional part, and $\text{mod}(x, y)$ returns
63 the remainder on dividing x by y (x modulo y).

64 **Program 4.7.** Program for Smarandache's function.

$$\mu(n) := \begin{cases} \text{return } \text{"Err. } n \text{ nu este intreg"} \text{ if } n \neq \text{trunc}(n) \\ \text{return } \text{"Err. } n < 1" \text{ if } n < 1 \\ \text{return } (1) \text{ if } n=1 \\ f \leftarrow Fa(n) \\ p \leftarrow f^{(1)} \\ \alpha \leftarrow f^{(2)} \\ \text{for } k = 1..rows(p) \\ \quad \eta_k \leftarrow p_k \cdot Nbg(\alpha_k, p_k) \cdot b(\alpha_k, p_k) \\ \text{return } \max(\eta) \end{cases}$$

65 This program calls the $Fa(n)$ factorization with prime numbers. The program uses the Smaran-
 66 dache’s Remark 3 – about the Kempner algorithm. The $\mu.prn$ file generation is done once. The
 67 reading of this generated file in Mathcad’s documents results in a great time–save.

68 **Program 4.8.** Program with which the file $\mu.prn$ is generated

```
VFμ(N) := | μ1 ← 1
           | for n ∈ 2..N
           |   μn ← μ(n)
           | return μ
```

69 This program calls the program 4.7 for calculating the value of the μ function. The sequence of
 70 the $\mu.prn$ file generation is:

```
t0 := time(0) WRITEPRN("μ.prn") := VFμ(2 · 107) t1 := time(1)
```

```
71 (t1 – t0)sec = "5 : 17 : 32.625"hhmmss
```

72 Smarandache’s function is important because it characterizes prime numbers – through the
 73 following fundamental property:

74 **Theorem 4.9.** Let be p an integer > 4 , than p is prime number if and only if $\mu(p) = p$.

75 *Proof.* See (Smarandache, 1999, p. 31). □

76 Hence, the fixed points of this function are prime numbers (to which is added 4). Due to this
 77 property the function is used as primality test.

78 **Program 4.10.** Program for testing μ ’s primality. This program returns the 0 value if the number
 79 is not prime number and the 1 value if the number is a prime. The file $\mu.prn$ will be read and it
 80 will be assigned to the μ vector.

```
ORIGIN := 1 μ := READPRN("... \μ.prn")
```

```
Tpμ(n) := | return "Err. n < 1 sau n ∉ ℤ" if n < 1 ∨ n ≠ trunc(n)
           | if n > 4
           |   return 0 if μn ≠ n
           |   return 1 otherwise
           | otherwise
           |   return 0 if n=1 ∨ n=4
           |   return 1 otherwise
```

81 **Program 4.11.** Program that provides the reverses of the given m number.

$$R(m) := \begin{array}{l} n \leftarrow \text{floor}(\log(m)) \\ x \leftarrow m \cdot 10^{-n} \\ \text{for } k \in 1..n \\ \quad \left| \begin{array}{l} c_k \leftarrow \text{trunc}(x) \\ x \leftarrow (x - c_k) \cdot 10 \end{array} \right. \\ c_{n+1} \leftarrow \text{round}(x) \\ Rm \leftarrow 0 \\ \text{for } k \in n + 1..2 \\ \quad Rm \leftarrow (Rm + c_k) \cdot 10 \\ \text{return } Rm + c_1 \end{array}$$

82 Where $\text{floor}(x)$ returns the greatest integer $\leq x$ and $\text{round}(x)$ returns x rounded to the nearest
83 integer.

84 **Program 4.12.** Search program for the Luhn prime numbers.

$$PLuhn(L) := \begin{array}{l} n \leftarrow \text{last}(p) \\ S \leftarrow (229) \\ k \leftarrow 51 \\ \text{while } p_k \leq L \\ \quad \left| \begin{array}{l} N \leftarrow R(p_k) + p_k \\ S \leftarrow \text{stack}(S, p_k) \text{ if } T p \mu(N) = 1 \\ k \leftarrow k + 1 \end{array} \right. \\ \text{return } S \end{array}$$

85 The function $\text{stack}(A, B, \dots)$ is applied for merging matrixes top-down. The number of columns in
86 matrixes should also be the same. The discussed functions could be applied to vectors as well.

87 Execution of the program $PLuhn$ was made with sequence

$$S := PLuhn(2 \cdot 10^7)$$

88 The initialization of the S stack is done with the vector that contains the number 229. The
89 variable k has the initial value of 51 because the index of the 229 prime number is 50, so that the
90 search for the *Luhn prime numbers* will begin with $p_{51} = 233$.

91 5. List of prime numbers Luhn

92 We present a partial list of the 50598 *Luhn prime numbers* smaller than $2 \cdot 10^7$ (the first 321
93 and the last 120):

94 229, 239, 241, 257, 269, 271, 277, 281, 439, 443, 463, 467, 479, 499, 613, 641, 653, 661, 673, 677,
95 683, 691, 811, 823, 839, 863, 881, 20011, 20029, 20047, 20051, 20101, 20161, 20201, 20249,
96 20269, 20347, 20389, 20399, 20441, 20477, 20479, 20507, 20521, 20611, 20627, 20717, 20759,
97 20809, 20879, 20887, 20897, 20981, 21001, 21019, 21089, 21157, 21169, 21211, 21377, 21379,
98 21419, 21467, 21491, 21521, 21529, 21559, 21569, 21577, 21601, 21611, 21617, 21647, 21661,

99 21701, 21727, 21751, 21767, 21817, 21841, 21851, 21859, 21881, 21961, 21991, 22027, 22031,
 100 22039, 22079, 22091, 22147, 22159, 22171, 22229, 22247, 22291, 22367, 22369, 22397, 22409,
 101 22469, 22481, 22501, 22511, 22549, 22567, 22571, 22637, 22651, 22669, 22699, 22717, 22739,
 102 22741, 22807, 22859, 22871, 22877, 22961, 23017, 23021, 23029, 23081, 23087, 23099, 23131,
 103 23189, 23197, 23279, 23357, 23369, 23417, 23447, 23459, 23497, 23509, 23539, 23549, 23557,
 104 23561, 23627, 23689, 23747, 23761, 23831, 23857, 23879, 23899, 23971, 24007, 24019, 24071,
 105 24077, 24091, 24121, 24151, 24179, 24181, 24229, 24359, 24379, 24407, 24419, 24439, 24481,
 106 24499, 24517, 24547, 24551, 24631, 24799, 24821, 24847, 24851, 24889, 24979, 24989, 25031,
 107 25057, 25097, 25111, 25117, 25121, 25169, 25171, 25189, 25219, 25261, 25339, 25349, 25367,
 108 25409, 25439, 25469, 25471, 25537, 25541, 25621, 25639, 25741, 25799, 25801, 25819, 25841,
 109 25847, 25931, 25939, 25951, 25969, 26021, 26107, 26111, 26119, 26161, 26189, 26209, 26249,
 110 26251, 26339, 26357, 26417, 26459, 26479, 26489, 26591, 26627, 26681, 26701, 26717, 26731,
 111 26801, 26849, 26921, 26959, 26981, 27011, 27059, 27061, 27077, 27109, 27179, 27239, 27241,
 112 27271, 27277, 27281, 27329, 27407, 27409, 27431, 27449, 27457, 27479, 27481, 27509, 27581,
 113 27617, 27691, 27779, 27791, 27809, 27817, 27827, 27901, 27919, 28001, 28019, 28027, 28031,
 114 28051, 28111, 28229, 28307, 28309, 28319, 28409, 28439, 28447, 28571, 28597, 28607, 28661,
 115 28697, 28711, 28751, 28759, 28807, 28817, 28879, 28901, 28909, 28921, 28949, 28961, 28979,
 116 29009, 29017, 29021, 29027, 29101, 29129, 29131, 29137, 29167, 29191, 29221, 29251, 29327,
 117 29389, 29411, 29429, 29437, 29501, 29587, 29629, 29671, 29741, 29759, 29819, 29867, 29989,
 118 ...
 119 8990143, 8990209, 8990353, 8990441, 8990563, 8990791, 8990843, 8990881, 8990929, 8990981,
 120 8991163, 8991223, 8991371, 8991379, 8991431, 8991529, 8991553, 8991613, 8991743, 8991989,
 121 8992069, 8992091, 8992121, 8992153, 8992189, 8992199, 8992229, 8992259, 8992283, 8992483,
 122 8992493, 8992549, 8992561, 8992631, 8992861, 8992993, 8993071, 8993249, 8993363, 8993401,
 123 8993419, 8993443, 8993489, 8993563, 8993723, 8993749, 8993773, 8993861, 8993921, 8993951,
 124 8994091, 8994109, 8994121, 8994169, 8994299, 8994463, 8994473, 8994563, 8994613, 8994721,
 125 8994731, 8994859, 8994871, 8994943, 8995003, 8995069, 8995111, 8995451, 8995513, 8995751,
 126 8995841, 8995939, 8996041, 8996131, 8996401, 8996521, 8996543, 8996651, 8996681, 8996759,
 127 8996831, 8996833, 8996843, 8996863, 8996903, 8997059, 8997083, 8997101, 8997463, 8997529,
 128 8997553, 8997671, 8997701, 8997871, 8997889, 8997931, 8997943, 8997979, 8998159, 8998261,
 129 8998333, 8998373, 8998411, 8998643, 8998709, 8998813, 8998919, 8999099, 8999161, 8999183,
 130 8999219, 8999311, 8999323, 8999339, 8999383, 8999651, 8999671, 8999761, 8999899, 8999981 .

131 6. Conclusions

132 The list of all *Luhn prime numbers*, that totaled 50598 numbers, was determined within a
 133 time span of 54 seconds, on an Intel processor of 2.20 GHz.

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